

PQC Appendices List

June, 2025

Appendix A. EC3 x EC10

Appendix B. EC2 x EC11

Appendix C. Glossary

Internet protocols glossary	
IP	Internet Protocol.
IPsec	Internet Protocol security.
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol.
UDP	User Datagram Protocol.
FTP	File Transfer Protocol.
TLS	Transport Layer Security.
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol.
SSH	Secure Shell.
NTP	Network Time Protocol.
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport.
SRTP	Secure Real-time Transport Protocol.
IKEv2	Internet Key Exchange version 2.
DNS	Domain Name System.
DNSSEC	Domain Name System Security Extensions.
3PAKE	Three-Party Authenticated Key Exchange.

Classical cryptographic algorithms glossary	
RSA	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman.
ECC	Elliptic Curve Cryptography.
DSA	Digital Signature Algorithm.
3DES	Triple Data Encryption Standard.
SHA	Secure Hash Algorithm.
MD5	Message Digest Algorithm 5.

Post-Quantum Cryptographic (PQC) algorithms glossary	
SPHINCS+	Subset Preserving Hash-based Signature Compressed Scheme.
NTRU	Fast-Fourier Lattice-based Compact Signatures Over NTRU.
FALCON	Fast Fourier Lattice-based Signature Scheme.
CSIDH	Commutative Supersingular Isomorphism Diffie-Hellman.
SIKE	Supersingular Isogeny Key Encapsulation.
GeMSS	Great Multivariate Short Signature.

Appendix D. Catalog for PQC implementation in internet protocols

Protocol	Algorithm Primitive	PQC Algorithm	Research Gaps	Research Status	Applications
IP	None	None	Completely unaddressed in current research.	Unexplored	None
IPsec	Lattice-Based	Kyber Dilithium	Limited focus on energy and bandwidth optimization.	Partially explored	VPN connections Data integrity
TCP	None	None	No research on integrating PQC into TCP protocol.	Unexplored	None
UDP	None	None	No studies focusing on UDP with PQC solutions.	Unexplored	None
FTP	None	None	Unexplored protocol in the context of PQC.	Unexplored	None
TLS	Lattice-Based Hash-Based	Kyber Dilithium SPHINCS+	High computational overhead; limited energy efficiency studies.	Extensively studied	Web traffic Secure communication
DHCP	None	None	No research on PQC adaptations for DHCP.	Unexplored	None
SSH	Lattice-Based	NTRU Kyber	Minimal focus on practical integration and resource constraints.	Underexplored	Remote access Server management
NTP	None	None	Completely absent from PQC-related studies.	Unexplored	None
Kerberos	None	None	No studies exploring Kerberos with PQC solutions.	Unexplored	None
MQTT	Lattice-Based	Kyber SPHINCS+	Limited scalability and resource efficiency testing for IoT applications.	Partially explored	IoT communications
SRTP	None	None	No studies on securing real-time transport protocols with PQC.	Unexplored	None

Appendix E. Catalog for PQC implementation in internet protocols

Criterion	Category	# Measures	%
Domain of Necessity	Hardware	4	9
	Software	4	9
	Net Protocols	27	61
	Bandwidth	1	2
	Energy	2	5
	Compute Power	5	11
	Other	1	2
Type of System	Legacy	2	4
	Embedded	11	23
	Distributed	14	29
	Cloud	9	19
	No Specified	11	23
	Other	1	2
Stage of Interest	Handshake	10	29
	Key Encapsulation	4	11
	Key Exchange	16	46
	No Specified	5	14
	Other	0	0
Classical Algorithms	RSA	7	17
	ECC	5	13
	DSA	1	3
	Diffie Hellman	4	10
	3DES	0	0
	SHA	2	5
	MD5	0	0
	No Specified	21	52
	Other	0	0
Classical Protocols	IP	0	0
	IPSec	5	12
	TCP	1	2
	UDP	0	0
	FTP	0	0
	TLS	16	38
	DHCP	0	0
	SSH	1	2
	NTP	0	0
	Kerberos	0	0
	MQTT	1	2
	SRTP	0	0
	No Specified	8	19
	Other	10	24
	Impacted Sector	Healthcare	5
Military		4	7
Government		12	21
Entertainment		1	2
Social Media		1	2
Business		7	12
Industrial		9	16
Finance		5	9
No Specified		13	22
Other		0	0

Affected Device	Switch	3	8
	Router	4	10
	Access Point	0	0
	PC/Laptop	2	5
	Smartphone	0	0
	IoT devices	12	30
	Firewall	0	0
	NIC	0	0
	Modem	0	0
	No Specified	17	43
	Other	2	5
Quantum Algorithms	SPHINCS+	3	4
	FALCON	8	11
	Dilithium	13	18
	Kyber	17	24
	NTRU	6	8
	CSIDH	0	0
	SIKE	3	4
	GeMSS	1	1
	Rainbow	1	1
	No Specified	10	14
	Other	9	13
Algorithm Primitives	Lattice	20	45
	Isogeny	3	7
	LWE	4	9
	RLWE	1	2
	Hash	6	14
	Code	3	7
	Multivariate	3	7
	No Specified	4	9
	Other	0	0
Improves Protocol	Yes	29	85
	No	5	15
Type of Solution	Algorithm	2	5
	Protocol	25	62
	Architecture	7	18
	Framework	6	15
	Other	0	0
Type of Validation	Study of case	10	25
	Proof of concepts	8	20
	Experiment	13	32
	Quasi experiment	0	0
	Survey	2	5
	No specified	4	10
	Other	3	8
Approach Scope	Industry	11	34
	Academy	21	66

Appendix F. Journal Ranking

Conference/Journal	Core/Quartile	Found Papers
Computer and Communications Security (CCS)	A	1
SECURITY AND PRIVACY	Not Ranked	0
Software - Practice and Experience	Q2	0